

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

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EVIDENCED-BASED RECOMMENDATIONS FOR IMPROVING
COLLABORATIVE PRACTICE FOR VETERANS

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

The Veterans Healthcare Administration spends 67% of their budget caring for those with chronic illnesses. Addressing the health needs of veterans with multiple chronic conditions requires an interdisciplinary collaborative approach. Collaboration is a process of interactions between healthcare providers that is constant, frequent, and productive. Collaboration requires that all individuals actively engage in processes that facilitate team-based behaviors to meet patient care goals. The purpose of this DNP project was to develop evidence-based recommendations that improve the collaborative practices among healthcare providers caring for veterans.

Two hundred sixty-seven palliative care providers from 50 states and 7 countries participated in an online survey and provided qualitative responses to one of two questions: (1) Please describe any thoughts you may have about interdisciplinary teams (IDTs), collaboration, and quality of care? After collecting 86 responses, the open-ended question was modified to read: (2) Can you describe a time when IDT collaboration or communication made a difference in the quality of care for your patients? Modification of the question resulted in 181 responses from participants. Responses were coded and categorized to identify themes about communication and collaboration. Three themes arose from the analysis: collaboration, communication, and IDT. These themes provided insight into the concept of collaboration and its importance in patient care. The

qualitative themes informed the development of recommendations based on a review of the literature and the TeamSTEPPS conceptual model.

Respondents provided exemplars of collaboration and communication processes, their influence on patient and family outcomes. Participants depicted collaboration as a shared interaction among team members that “requires trust, respect, and frequent communication.” Respondents described communication as being “vital,” “important” and “key” that involves frequent and consistent sharing of information to meet patient and family needs. Lastly, IDTs were described as being “essential,” “effective,” and “crucial,” involving various healthcare providers from different disciplines to optimize outcomes. Each of these key elements contributed to the understanding of collaboration and supported the significance of a team-based approach in enhancing patient and family care experiences.

Providers characterized collaboration as working together, contributing their knowledge and expertise to meet patient and family care goals. Further research on collaboration can assist in identifying key facilitators and barriers of collaboration to standardize processes used in clinical settings. Standardization can mitigate fragmentation in communication and collaboration resulting in improved patient outcomes. Collaboration should be the standard approach in care delivery. Ultimately, collaboration will lead to a clinical culture of cohesiveness and shared decision-making that should be encouraged and promoted by healthcare leaders.

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BACKGROUND

Patients with chronic, complex health needs receive care from different medical providers in various clinical settings. For clinicians, this makes continuity of care, optimal treatment, and care coordination difficult (Hartgerink et al., 2014).

As the population ages, healthcare costs will rise over the next decade (Bodenhemier, Chen, & Bennett, 2009; Kinney et al., 2015). Patients with complex needs require the collaboration of multiple providers from various disciplines to care for them (Nolte & McKee, 2008). A collaborative approach among providers improves quality of care, decreases medical errors, and prevents poor health outcomes (Haynes & Strickler, 2014).

Collaboration is a process of interaction and communication between healthcare providers (Bedwell et al., 2012). Optimal collaboration can maximize treatment options for patients (Bedwell et al., 2012; Ushiro & Nakayma, 2010; Xyrichis & Ream, 2008). Collaborative team members share goals and participate in decision making that supports patient care (Institute of Medicine [IOM], 2011; Plonien & Williams, 2015). Team members have mutual respect for one another and value the clinical recommendations of each provider (IOM, 2011; Plonien & Williams, 2015). Although the definition of the term varies, Chrislip (2002) defines collaboration as “mutually beneficial relationships between two or more parties who work together toward common goals by sharing responsibility, authority, and accountability for achieving results” (p. 41). Chrislip’s definition was the operational meaning of collaboration used for this project.

Additionally, communication plays an integral role in the collaborative process. It involves sharing information between healthcare team members. However, when

information is inaccurate or incomplete, it impedes collaborative efforts and leads to poor patient outcomes (Donaldson et al., 2000; M. Johnson, Sanchez, & Zheng, 2016).

Ultimately, communication facilitates the collaborative process.

The IOM (1999) report, *To Err Is Human: Building a Safer Health System*, raised awareness of the impact of fragmented communication and its effects on patient care.

Communication failures among healthcare providers contribute to errors and increase patient risk for morbidity and mortality (Donaldson et al., 2000). Hassmiller (2014)

found that knowledge communication deficits in healthcare increased awareness among providers as to the challenges in formulating and sustaining integrated teams.

Collaborative teams address complex patient issues by communicating and using their vast knowledge with other team members to achieve care goals. Providers who share

their knowledge and expertise facilitate the development and implementation of interventions that are comprehensive as well as patient centered (IOM, 2011).

Collaboration aims to enhance quality patient care and improve clinical practice (Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services, 2016).

Problem Statement

Adults age 65 and older account for approximately 14% of the population in the United States. This group will increase to approximately 20% of the population by the year 2040 (U.S. Department of Health & Human Services, 2016). Within this elderly population, there are millions of veterans with complex health needs who would benefit from a collaborative care model. The number of veterans with complex healthcare needs has increased since World War I (Allen, Armstrong, Conrad, Saladimer, & Hamilton, 2013). According to Jakupcak and Varra (2011), about 900,000 veterans have separated

from active duty and are currently accessing medical services. Nearly 42% of the veteran population receives medical care from the Veterans Health Administration (VHA) healthcare system (Jakupcak & Varra, 2011). Moreover, at least one out of three veterans suffers from three or more chronic conditions. Addressing the needs of veterans with chronic illnesses accounts for almost 67% of VHA healthcare cost (Balbale, Etingen, Malhoit, Miskevics, & Lavela, 2016; Yoon, Zulman, Scott, & Maciejewski, 2014). Due to their complex healthcare needs, veterans experience a higher rate of poor health outcomes when compared to the general population (Balbale et al., 2016).

The VHA healthcare system is a dynamic system that provides comprehensive services to a unique population. Veterans suffer from a multitude of chronic illnesses that hinder or limit physical and mental capacity. This population requires an interdisciplinary approach to care that is specific to their needs in and out of the hospital. The VHA strives to sustain an environment based on this model of care, which is why patients are generally satisfied with VHA care compared to other healthcare institutions, according to the U.S. Department of Veterans Affairs (2017). Outcomes about the quality of care provided by VHA facilities are measured using tools such as the strategic analytics for improvement and learning approach (SAIL) and the survey of healthcare experiences of patients (SHEP).

The scores generated by these tools identify deficient and proficient areas in care delivery related to measures regarding timely effective care, re-admission rates, death rates, patient satisfaction, communication during care delivery, responsiveness of hospital staff, transitions of care, cleanliness of hospital environment, and quietness of hospital environment. This information is gathered each fiscal year, and an overall star ranking

score of 1 to 5 (1 meaning low quality and 5 meaning high quality) is given based upon results. According to the U.S. Department of Veterans Affairs (2017), for the 2016 fiscal year, 67% (98 out of 146) of VHA facilities received a rating score of 3 or below and 32% (48 out of 146) received a score of 4 or 5. The same results were reported for the fiscal year of 2017. The scores demonstrate disconnect in the care provided and veterans' perceptions about the care they receive.

The core measures monitored for quality of care at VHA facilities require healthcare providers to have a clear and mutual understanding of one another's role and limitations to ensure veterans' needs are adequately met to optimize outcomes for this population. The key drivers of performance improvement are the current models of care and the potential solutions that will enhance and bring about change to the current care model. If the goals are safe and effective care, decreased adverse events, and improved patient satisfaction, all approaches should be used until goals are met. Past VHA studies found positive correlations between teamwork culture and patient satisfaction as well as teamwork culture and nurse turnover (Mohr, Burgess, & Young, 2008).

Because no single healthcare provider can address all the complex needs of a veteran with multiple morbidities, it is imperative that care delivery for veterans includes an interdisciplinary collaborative approach to their care. There is extensive literature that supports the importance of collaboration and communication for optimal IDT functioning (Bedwell et al., 2012; Caricati et al., 2014; Caricati et al., 2015; Hartgerink et al., 2014; Haynes & Strickler, 2014; King et al., 2008; Lee, Mills, & Neily, 2014; Meredith et al., 2016; Rose, 2011; Rycroft-Malone et al., 2016; Weinberg, Cooney-Miner, Perloff, Babington, & Avgar, 2011; Zwarenstein, Goldman, & Reeves, 2009). However, empiric

evidence related to healthcare providers' perceptions regarding the influence of collaboration on patient care is limited. Provider perceptions about whether or not collaboration exists or what collaboration looks like are inconsistent. While some researchers endorse the benefits of multidisciplinary partnerships in patient care, others indicate a lack of follow-through at times when collaboration should have occurred but did not (Lancaster, Kolakowsky-Hayner, Kovacich, & Greer-Williams, 2015; Maztziou et al., 2014; Robinson, Gorman, Slimmer, & Yudkowsky, 2010; Weinberg et al., 2011). In addition, formal recommendations for translating empiric data into clinical practice to improve veteran care are lacking.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this DNP project was to improve the care of veterans based on healthcare provider perceptions and exemplars of interdisciplinary communication and collaboration. To this end, the objectives of this DNP project were to:

1. Conduct a content analysis of written responses to an existing survey regarding interdisciplinary collaboration in relation to care quality.
2. Develop practice recommendations based upon themes that emerge from the qualitative analysis to improve collaborative care for veterans across healthcare settings.

Theoretical Framework

According to Bonnel and Smith (2014), theories, frameworks, or conceptual models serve as a foundation for clinical projects. Frameworks provide guidance in defining and organizing various concepts so that the goals of clinical projects can be described (Bonnel & Smith, 2014). A framework should be logical, useful, simple, and centered on the scope of the clinical project (Bonnel & Smith, 2014). Furthermore, frameworks provide the lens through which the problem can be investigated and allow

researchers to examine correlating relationships among concepts. The Team Strategies and Tools to Enhance Performance and Patient Safety (TeamSTEPPS) model was chosen to serve as the supporting framework for this DNP project.

TeamSTEPPS

The idea of team-based care or healthcare teams is not a new phenomenon. As previously mentioned, the IOM's (1999) report, *To Err Is Human: Building a Safer Health System*, identified various deficits in communication among healthcare providers that affected patient outcomes and threatened care quality. This report fueled the development of initiatives that fostered and facilitated a team-based approach to care (Sheppard, Williams, & Klein, 2013). Using and implementing evidence-based practices provide the best approaches to ensure patients receive safe and effective care. The TeamSTEPPS is a teamwork model developed in 2006 by the U.S. Department of Defense and the Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (AHRQ) to provide healthcare professionals with tools that assist them in efficiently functioning as a team (King et al., 2008). This model aims to improve the dynamics of healthcare professionals and their environment by providing learning tools for enhancing collaboration and communication strategies in clinical settings.

The collaborative process is embedded within the TeamSTEPPS model. Thus, the TeamSTEPPS model guided the DNP author in understanding how healthcare providers can best function as a collaborative team to improve health outcomes. Furthermore, TeamSTEPPS is a standardized training curriculum that promotes team-based care for healthcare providers and optimizes patient outcomes by focusing on four competencies: (a) communication, (b) leadership, (c) situation monitoring, and (d) mutual support. The

combination of the four skills fosters the development of partnerships and goal-oriented interactions among providers that facilitate improved decision making during care planning. Components of this model help shape the processes involved in collaboration and communication.

Communication. According to the Joint Commission (2015), ineffective communication was one of the most frequently identified causes of reported sentinel events in 2015, which is why communication is critical in healthcare settings. Communication is a competency integral to the TeamSTEPPS model and involves using tools or strategies to promote effective team interactions (Plonien & Williams, 2015). Communication includes verbal, written, and electronic methods of sharing information to achieve a mutual goal. Processes such as Situation, Background, Assessment and Recommendation (SBAR) hand-off report, check-back, and call-out are strategies that enable healthcare providers to discuss essential aspects of the patient's conditions to determine what action or approach to employ during care delivery (Plonien & Williams, 2015). The use of SBAR increases effective communication among providers. Promoting the use of communication tools during transitions of care and care planning activities decreases information omission and uncertainty, optimizes information, and prevents fragmented patient care (Clapper & Kong, 2012; Plonien & Williams, 2015).

The transfer or exchange of information should occur between team members as well as with outside healthcare providers to reduce errors and improve patient outcomes (Plonien & Williams, 2015). Sharing relevant patient information is required between team members and the community to develop a variety of treatment approaches and engage in discussions about care goals. The exchange of information occurs during (a)

interdepartmental transfer of care, (b) transitions of care to and from various levels of care, and (c) from different healthcare providers at multiple institutions (Weller, Boyd, & Cumin, 2014). The communication should be clear, concise, and understood by those involved in patient care (Weller et al., 2014).

Information sharing promotes collaboration between institutions and providers, which facilitates continuity of care and results in better patient outcomes (Mazzocco et al., 2009; Toccafondi et al., 2012). Furthermore, communicating with outside institutions (i.e., diagnostic agencies, hospitals/clinics/private practice, rehabilitation facilities, and nursing homes) assists in the improvement of patient outcomes by expanding care options and identifying various prevention strategies to address patient needs (Bowen et al., 2010; Gugiu, Westine, Coryn, & Hobson, 2013; Wagner et al., 2001). In developing practice recommendations for this project, the DNP author considered how communication promotes collaboration and enhances veterans' care.

Leadership. Leadership in the TeamSTEPPS model involves administrative personnel or team leaders organizing a team, developing a team model, and defining team functions as well as responsibilities (Plonien & Williams, 2015). According to the AHRQ (2014), the leadership competency involves leaders providing an environment for shared knowledge, monitoring team performance, coordinating and directing team activities, providing feedback, and modifying collaborative models to ensure sustainment of healthcare teams. Additionally, healthcare leaders (i.e., directors, CEOs, managers, supervisors) in clinical practice settings are responsible for creating a culture that promotes and supports teamwork (Bethea, Holland, & Reddick, 2014) by making collaboration the standard in clinical practice settings. The IOM (2011, 2015)

emphasized the importance of healthcare organizations encouraging all health professionals to work in groups to enforce shared responsibility and collective understanding of patient needs (IOM, 2011, 2015).

Healthcare leaders should devote time to promote team activities such as care planning meetings, team-building efforts, and team-based process improvement tasks that increase collaboration (Bethea et al., 2014; Weller, Barrow, & Gasquoine, 2011).

Leaders are accountable for formulating goals and removing barriers that interfere with the facilitation of team-based care (Bethea et al., 2014). Healthcare providers should be encouraged to be interdependent and rely on team members to address patient care needs using collaborative skills (Gugiu et al., 2013). Healthcare organizations should implement interprofessional curriculums that educate and train healthcare providers on (a) the structure of integrated teams, (b) how to work in teams, (c) the relationship between collaboration and patient outcomes, and (d) how to sustain collaborative relationships (Panel, 2011; Schmitt, Blue, Aschenbrener, & Viggiano, 2011). In developing practice recommendations for this project, the DNP author considered how leadership within the VHA could facilitate the development and sustainment of strong collaborative teams.

Situation Monitoring. Situation monitoring in the TeamSTEPPS model, also known as mutual performance monitoring, involves providing feedback to others and identifying needs of the healthcare team to prevent discrepancy or misunderstanding (Plonien & William, 2015). The result is the promotion of effective team interactions (Plonien & Williams, 2015). Situation monitoring requires team members to employ situational awareness. Situational awareness consists of clinicians not only being aware

of their own skills and limitations, but those of the other team members, with the goal of facilitating mutual understanding. Having an awareness of personal skills and the skills of others is a vital component of mutual performance monitoring. The knowledge of patient status, environment, and care delivery goals are essential to ensure that shared goals are achieved, and decision making is cohesive. This level of competency fosters mutual respect and team accountability and facilitates cross-monitoring (Clancy & Tornberg, 2007) by encouraging team members to monitor each other's behaviors. Cross-monitoring ensures that task execution is effective (AHRQ, 2014). The process of cross-monitoring promotes workload sharing, priority setting, and mutual understanding of what is affecting the operational functioning of the team (AHRQ, 2014). Furthermore, situation monitoring ensures team members are on the same page, communication is synchronized, and they engage in active problem solving as a unit versus separate entities. In developing practice recommendations for this project, the DNP author considered how situation monitoring would enhance collaboration within the VHA healthcare system.

Mutual Support. Mutual support in the TeamSTEPPS model involves team members sharing responsibility, building trust, and providing feedback to each other to sustain positive interactions (Clapper & Kong, 2012; Plonien & Williams, 2015). Unlike the leadership competency where the leader is providing feedback for improvement, the team members are establishing a culture for constructive discussion about how to enhance team processes. Healthcare providers in the team approach are accountable for their care planning decisions, are active participants when collaborating with team members, and demonstrate behaviors that sustain proactive collaborative interactions.

Healthcare providers need to ensure that their actions foster teamwork and interdependence. Succinct, realistic goals and plans of care will facilitate follow-up of the patient's health status among team members. Defining roles and tasks of the healthcare team may prevent interruption in workflow, promote effective communication, and enhance collaborative care for the patient (King et al., 2008). Furthermore, this component considers the accountability and self-initiative of the providers to be actively engaged in team-based care activities to optimize team performance. In developing practice recommendations for this project, the DNP author considered the role of or existence of mutual support in facilitating collaboration among healthcare providers within the VHA healthcare system.

TeamSTEPPS Model in this DNP Project

The four competencies from the TeamSTEPPS model (see Figure 1) supports communication and team processes to facilitate the collaborative approach needed to address complex health needs. This model, along with the evidence from the data used in this project, guided the development of succinct practice recommendations to enhance collaborative care at the VHA.

Summary

The TeamSTEPPS competencies ensure that teamwork is integrated into practice by promoting trust and mutual goal setting among team members. TeamSTEPPS affirms that roles and responsibilities are clearly defined among team members. Furthermore, this team-based model is designed to improve patient safety while enhancing teamwork skills and producing high functioning teams by incorporating all four competencies in healthcare settings. If healthcare providers are equipped with tools to empower, educate,

and support team members during care delivery activities, they would not perceived collaboration as challenging.

Figure 1. TeamSTEPPS: Supporting team-based care. Adapted and modified from “TeamSTEPPS 2.0 Curriculum” by the Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality, 2014. Retrieved from <http://www.ahrq.gov/teamstepps>.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Overview

A review of the literature examined the influence of collaborative care on (a) patient outcomes, (b) healthcare providers' perceptions of collaborative practice, and (c) facilitators and barriers of collaborative practice. The literature search included the following databases: Academic Search Premier, Cochrane Library, PsychInfo, PsyArticles, CINAHL, PubMed, and Google Scholar. Search terms included “nurs* and perception and team*,” “nurs* and collaborat*,” “collaborative care,” “team* and nurs*,” and “collabo* and patient outcomes.” Inclusion criteria consisted of peer-reviewed articles published in English from 2007 to 2017. The literature identified both qualitative and quantitative research.

Goebel, Guo, and Wood (2016) conducted a study exploring teamwork and perceptions of care quality in a palliative care setting. This study identified team structures and processes that influence perceptions of care quality (Goebel et al., 2016). The 50-item web-based survey included items related to demographic and clinical practice information, team processes (based upon the TeamSTEPPS model), and perceptions of care quality (Goebel et al., 2016). Quantitative analysis revealed that positive perceptions of care quality were associated with formal team membership, providers who collaborated with more disciplines, providers who worked in nonacute care settings, male providers, and providers with higher levels of education (Goebel et al., 2016). Furthermore, the TeamSTEPPS model was associated with positive perceptions of care quality. The present project analyzed two open-ended questions included in the

survey to identify themes related to collaboration and communication among healthcare providers not previously examined as part of the Goebel et al. (2016) study.

The World Health Organization (WHO) has emphasized the importance of collaborative care in healthcare settings (Engle & Prentice, 2013). As the needs of the aging population become more complex, a collaborative approach to healthcare will become increasingly important (Engle & Prentice, 2013). Collaboration among healthcare providers is believed to be the key to improving patient care and optimizing health outcomes (Hassmiller, 2014).

Perceptions of Collaboration

Collaboration involves proactive interactions among healthcare providers from various disciplines sharing information, setting goals, and facilitating problem-solving strategies to address patient health needs (Bedwell et al., 2012; King et al., 2008; Ushiro & Nakayma, 2010; Xyrichis & Ream, 2008). Healthcare teams employ a comprehensive approach to care delivery. Studies identify collaboration as inclusion of providers from other disciplines to improve patient outcomes (Bayliss, Bhardwaja, Ross, Beck, & Lanese, 2011; Gerson & Gerson, 2003; Hedegaard et al., 2015; Hirsch et al., 2014; Katon et al., 2010; McAdam-Marx, Dahal, Jennings, Singhai, & Gunning, 2015; Reidt et al., 2016; Rice et al., 2010; Truitt, Pina, Person-Rennell, & Angstman, 2013; Tsukamoto et al., 2014). These studies emphasize the role healthcare teams play in clinical settings and their contribution in facilitating quality care. Healthcare providers' perceptions of collaboration can influence team functioning and impact care delivery.

External and internal factors can influence provider perspectives regarding collaboration. Research suggests that perceptions of collaboration set the tone of the

team environment and determines effectiveness of team performance (Matziou et al., 2014). Research also indicates that prominent factors of poor collaboration include misconceptions of professional roles, lack of interprofessional education, and poor communication (Barnsteiner, Disch, Hall, Mayer, & Moore, 2007; Matziou et al., 2014; Miller, Riley, Davis, & Hansen, 2008; Orchard, 2010). The next sections discuss the influence of these factors on perceptions of collaboration.

Misconceptions of Professional Roles

Healthcare systems have been hierarchically driven for decades (Coopman, 2001). Traditionally, nurse and physician roles have been viewed as unequal (Qolohle, Conradie, Ogunbanjo, & Malete, 2006). Physicians have long been characterized as dominant and nurses as dependent, resulting in a hierarchical approach versus a collaborative approach to patient care (Qolohle et al., 2006; Weinberg et al., 2011). Healthcare systems placing physicians in a patriarchal role and nurses in a subservient role make collaboration challenging and influence how each profession perceives one another's role in the patient care process (Delva, Jamiesin, & Lemieux, 2008; Matziou et al., 2014; Miller et al., 2008; Reeves, Nelson, & Zwarenstein, 2008; Weinberg et al., 2011).

Nurse-physician collaboration is the most highly studied team relationship; this may be due to the impact each role has on patient care. Although the two professions work closely together, nurses and physicians view collaboration differently (Matziou et al., 2014; Miller et al., 2008; Muller-Juge et al., 2013; Nair, et al., 2012; Robinson, Gorman, Slimmer, & Yudkowsky, 2010). Numerous studies found that the issue with nurse-physician collaboration is a lack of understanding professional roles (Matziou et al., 2014; Miller et al., 2008). Nurses view collaboration as a process of delegation rather

than a shared process (Weingberg et al., 2011). According to Lancaster, Kolakowsky-Hayner, Kovacich, and Greer-Williams (2015), nurses viewed themselves as solely, fulfilling orders formulated by the physician and felt that they were not listened to and physicians did not value their opinions. This study also found that nurses perceived physicians as “bossing them around” and possessing a superior attitude (Lancaster et al., 2015, p. 279). In the Robinson et al. (2010) study, nurses expressed how physicians lacked insight into the full scope of nursing practice, which hindered the ability of both parties to collaborate (Garber et al., 2009; Matziou et al., 2014).

It was determined that nurses were correct in their perceptions regarding how physicians viewed them. Physicians viewed collaboration with nurses as nurses following orders and serving the role of an assistant versus collaborative team member (Dillon, Noble, & Kaplan, 2009; Garber, Madigan, Click, & Firzpatrick, 2009). Physicians admitted to not fully understanding the role of the nurse other than carrying out orders and complying with decisions made by them (Casanova et al., 2007; Robinson et al., 2010). Lancaster et al. (2015) also explored the perceptions of collaboration among unlicensed assistive personnel, physicians, and nurses. A majority of physicians in this study did not know the purpose or role of unlicensed assistive personnel and had little to no interaction with them. Although physicians may have more interactions with nurses, they lacked insight into the roles of other professionals as well.

Physician perceptions of other healthcare providers' roles in patient care are problematic and can negatively affect collaboration. Löffler et al. (2017) explored interprofessional collaboration between general practitioners and community pharmacists. Physicians viewed the community pharmacist as being trained to “roll a

pill” (Löffler et al., 2017, p. 4) and, when discussing treatment orders over the phone, preferred to speak with the chief pharmacist versus other pharmacists. Pharmacists find it hard to collaborate with general practitioners regarding medication orders because of their resistive, disrespectful, and insulting attitude (Löffler et al., 2017). Physicians viewed pharmacists questioning their medication orders as clinically irrelevant. Physicians perceived themselves as more capable of making decisions about medication therapy compared to the pharmacist. This study is consistent with the nurse’s point of view that physicians perceive themselves as superior. This perception can be a barrier to collaboration.

Physicians view themselves as the primary decision maker when it comes to patient care (Lancaster et al., 2015). Likewise, nurses also view physicians as the primary decision maker and feel that physician authority supersedes their knowledge, resulting in nurses falling into a subservient role (Johnson & Kring, 2012; O’Leary et al., 2010). The fact that physicians view themselves as the primary decision maker forces them to place a diminished emphasis on collaboration, ultimately resulting in negative perceptions about team-based care (Garber et al., 2009). Furthermore, nurses accepting their role as more of an assistant to physicians may promote negative perceptions of collaboration among nurses (Johnson & Kring, 2012). There appears to be an established hierarchical order among providers that often is unspoken. Unfortunately, providers across all disciplines may lack knowledge about how to collaborate efficiently with one another.

Lack of Interprofessional Education

The lack of emphasis on developing intercollaborative partnerships during physician training promotes physicians to identify themselves as the authority and leader in healthcare (Wanzer, Wojtaszczyk, & Kelly, 2009). In comparison, nurses' perceptions of themselves as serving physicians is often reinforced through their training (Wanzer et al., 2009). The construct of collaboration and its importance in clinical practice is not emphasized in the curriculum of healthcare professionals, resulting in a silo approach to patient care (Rosenstein, 2002; Rosenstein, Russell, & Lauve, 2002). Besides, education across all disciplines occurs in silos (Barnsteiner et al., 2007; Rosenstein, 2002). Preparation in the classroom does not consist of interactions with other disciplines, thus once in practice, the same approach exists (Barnsteiner et al., 2007).

There is not enough in-depth instruction about the roles of other professions in relation to team-based care (Barnsteiner et al., 2007). The lack of formal education and standardized knowledge of collaboration promote the socialization of healthcare providers across all disciplines as isolated collaborators (Barnsteiner et al., 2007; Orchard, 2010; Weller et al., 2014). Consequently, healthcare professionals are reluctant to seek out assistance from other disciplines, thus preventing the development of collaborative relationships (Barnsteiner et al., 2007; Orchard, 2010). Furthermore, the lack of knowledge about and experience in how to collaborate deepens the gap among healthcare disciplines and impedes the development of healthcare teams. Expanding healthcare providers' knowledge about collaboration includes ensuring that healthcare providers function collaboratively and communicate effectively (Lisbon et al., 2016).

Poor Communication

Communication is a driving factor in collaboration and can determine the effectiveness of healthcare teams (Clapper & Kong, 2012; Lisbon et al., 2016).

Fragmented communication is the cause of medical errors, sentinel events, and failures in collaboration (IOM, 2011; The Joint Commission, 2014; Zwarenstein, Rice, Gotlib-Conn, Kenaszchuck, & Reeves, 2013). Communication breakdowns during transfers of care contribute significantly to medical errors (Blouin, 2011; Stagers & Blaz, 2013). Factors such as (a) inadequate time, (b) lack of standardized hand-off communication tools, (c) omission of information during transfers of information, and (d) work-flow interruptions can affect communication among providers (Blouin, 2011). In the Pollard, Miers, and Rickaby (2012) study, participants identified that breakdowns in communication occurred because of unclear task direction and assignment of responsibility. The assumption that one provider is taking care of a task, when, in actuality, the work is being done by another provider, or not being done at all, impacts care coordination (Pollard et al., 2012).

Successful communication occurs when information exchanges are complete, clear, brief, and timely (AHRQ, 2013). Healthcare providers use various routes of communication to exchange patient information. These involve verbal and electronic communications in which being direct and clear is essential. However, these communication routes are imperfect. According to Arnold and Boggs (2015), system failures, transmission failures, and reception failures are responsible for errors in communication. System failures occur when channels of communication within health institutions are complex or not used.

The electronic medical record (EMR) systems allow sharing of patient information among healthcare professionals. The EMR systems assist healthcare workers in providing safe and effective care while maintaining patient confidentiality and privacy. However, EMR systems may vary. Some healthcare institutions may employ a different EMR database or software that could be incompatible with what is used in another facility, making information sharing challenging. The electronic information systems are supposed to enhance the efficiency of communication and work productivity but instead may contribute to delays in care and miscommunication between providers (Robinson et al., 2010). Transmission failures occur when inaccurate or missing information is shared. Reception errors occur when information is misinterpreted, or accurate information is not retained (Arnold & Boggs, 2015). These types of mistakes create problems in patient care and can be attributed to time constraints, language or cultural barriers, lack of communication skills, and communication style (Arnold & Boggs, 2015). Training or annual competency testing in navigating and using the EMR systems should be employed by healthcare institutions and be considered a requirement for healthcare providers. The EMR system and other technological software is the primary communication method in healthcare. So, if healthcare providers are unable to navigate the EMR system or are unsure of where to find specific information in the EMR system, patient care, communication, and collaboration is affected. It is imperative that healthcare providers are educated on the functionality of EMR systems and are competent in managing software that involves patient information to ensure other providers involved in patient care have access to accurate information.

Conclusion

Overall, perceptions of collaboration vary among healthcare professionals; however, the consensus is that collaboration is fragmented as well as inconsistent. Healthcare team members should be cognizant of their limitations and capabilities as well as those of others. The scope of practice, education, and range of expertise should be considered by healthcare team members when completing patient care tasks to optimize team performance. It is also crucial for healthcare team members to be clear about how roles and responsibilities augment patient care and promote sustainment of an effective team environment.

New healthcare delivery models frequently include a focus on collaboration. Collaboration is identified as the essential component of clinical practice and the key to improving patient outcomes (Bedwell et al., 2012). According to the American Nurses Association, collaboration is also the standard and driving force of nursing practice, with the goal of improving patient outcomes (Moss, Seifert, & O'Sullivan, 2016). Inconsistent perceptions, role ambiguity, lack of respect, team inconsistency, defensiveness, workload, poor communication, and hierarchies are barriers to collaboration, thus making collaboration a challenging process in clinical practice settings (Dillion et al., 2009; Garber, Madigan, Click, & Firzpatrick, 2009; King et al., 2008; Lancaster et al., 2015; Rose, 2011; Weinberg et al., 2011).

METHODS

The overall goal of this DNP project was to develop practice recommendations to improve collaborative care for healthcare providers caring for veterans. To inform the development process and obtain a more thorough knowledge of communication and collaboration, the author coded and categorized qualitative responses to open-ended survey questions from an existing dataset (Goebel et al., 2016) to identify themes from the participants' responses. The Institutional Review Board (IRB) at California State University, Long Beach approved this project. Participants provided informed consent before providing their responses.

Design

The design used in this project to examine responses from the Goebel et al. (2016) survey was a qualitative content analysis. This design method allowed for interpretation of the content of text data to identify themes and patterns of responses through the process of coding (Zhang & Wildemuth, 2009). Conventional content analysis aims to describe and understand the phenomenon of interest (Hsieh & Shannon, 2005). This design allows the data to guide the development of concepts or constructs that explain and operationalize the social meaning of people's realities (Hsieh & Shannon, 2005). According to Polit and Beck (2017), content analysis is a descriptive qualitative approach that "produce(s) findings closer to the data" (p. 479). Ultimately, the goal of this approach is to condense expansive narrative responses into a familiar context that to be viewed in a new or different perspective (Zhang & Wildemuth, 2009).

Two open-ended questions were included in the survey: (1) Please describe any thoughts you may have about interdisciplinary teams (IDTs), collaboration, and quality of

care? and (2) Can you describe a time when IDT collaboration or communication made a difference in the quality of care for your patients? These questions allowed participants to use their own words narratively to explain the meaning of collaboration. Responses to each question were coded and analyzed for themes. Coding is an integral part of content analysis and guided the development of categories (Hsieh & Shannon, 2005). Three DNP program faculty members mentored and assisted the DNP author with the coding process to evaluate narrative responses. A standardized method regarding a coding scheme and coding consistency was employed to ensure intercoder reliability. This design approach was appropriate because open-ended responses of healthcare providers were analyzed. Healthcare providers in this study were involved in a team approach to patient care. Based on the content analysis, new emerging constructs regarding team-based care were discovered and used to support recommendations formulated in this project to improve care for veterans. Furthermore, these responses and the themes that evolved were compared to components of the TeamSTEPPS model to aid in the development of practice recommendations regarding collaboration and communication.

Sample/Setting

The Goebel et al. (2016) study used a purposive sampling method. Participants were included in their project if they self-identified as palliative care professionals. Providers worked in various practice settings (outpatient, acute care, hospice, and long-term care) within different parts of the world including the United States and four other countries (Bangladesh, Indonesia, England, and Asia). A total of 267 participants completed the survey. Various disciplines were represented including nurses, nurse aides, social workers, and physicians. About 81% of participants were nurses and almost

19% were other providers. Nearly all (90%) respondents were female. Many of the participants (49%) held higher education degrees of master's and above. A majority of the sample (96%) were of non-Hispanic descent (Goebel et al., 2016).

Survey

The original open-ended questions developed for the survey were modified shortly after study initiation to enhance responses. The first open-ended question was: Please describe any thoughts you may have about IDTs, collaboration, and quality of care. After 86 responses, the open-ended question was modified to read: Can you describe a time when IDT collaboration or communication made a difference in the quality of care for your patients? Modification of the question resulted in 181 responses from participants.

Data Collection

The qualitative data for this DNP project were obtained from an existing narrative dataset that examined how palliative care team structures and processes influenced healthcare professionals' perceptions of quality care in the palliative care setting (Goebel et al., 2016). A 50-item online survey was sent via email to all participants. Respondents had the option to participate in a lottery to win a \$50 gift card as an incentive for completing the survey. The study occurred from May 2013 to May 2014.

Data Analysis Procedures

The goal of content analysis was to provide an in-depth description of collaboration and to synthesize narrative responses into themes (Vaismoradi, Jones, Turunen, & Sneigrove, 2016). The author used an inductive coding approach to data analysis. Using an inductive method allowed for the emergence of themes to enhance

knowledge about the concept of collaboration versus testing a theory of collaboration (Polit & Beck, 2017). Because written text can have multiple meanings and can be subject to interpretation, it is essential to focus on the words written by participants and not employ personal perception during the data analysis process. The faculty mentors (researchers) and DNP author independently examined the data transcripts and assigned codes, wrote reflective notes, and sought out abstracts or concepts that provided a better understanding about the topic of interest (Vaismoradi et al., 2016). The DNP author and faculty mentors participated in the coding process, as team coding enhances reliability (Dierckx de Casterlé, Gastmans, Bryon, & Denier, 2011).

The DNP author and faculty reviewed and analyzed the data over several weeks, which involved reading written transcripts of participants' narrative responses and assigning a code to each statement. Every Monday, faculty and the DNP author would review the written transcripts and compare the codes that were identified. After reviewing and analyzing codes, the faculty and DNP author agreed on codes that best described the written text. When coding, words that were not congruent with patterns or themes were considered outliers and were not included in the final analysis (Dierckx de Casterlé et al., 2011). This systematic process gave researchers a holistic sense of the transcripts.

The DNP author and mentors individually highlighted and coded transcripts to identify key ideas. During this process, theoretical notes were kept to describe thoughts and notions about codes. It was essential to take note of different words used to express a feeling or emotion because the meaning of certain words may vary from person to person. Codes were then categorized into meaningful clusters (Hsieh & Shannon, 2005;

Vaismoradi et al., 2016) of categories and subcategories based on the relationships between individual codes. Clustering codes allowed the researchers to make sense of and determine linkages between codes.

After clustering codes into meaningful relationships, codes were labeled. Labeling codes allowed for an identified term or phrase to explain the meaning, feelings, and concepts generated by the written transcriptions (Vaismoradi et al., 2016). Classification and labeling of codes resulted in the generation of categories. Categories were analyzed to determine the primary themes that allowed faculty and the DNP author to make inferences about the data. As themes emerged, datasets were organized using a list format. This format helped to identify similar language patterns and recurring ideas found within the data. Analysis of categorized themes resulted in integration of critical concepts, language patterns, and recurring thoughts that guided the development of a general meaning for collaboration. The results from the data provided answers to the research questions as well as supported the relevance of the findings including the significance of collaboration in clinical settings. Lastly, the findings assisted in the identification of strategies to bring about change as well as to help improve collaboration and communication in healthcare settings.

Quality of Qualitative Inquiry

The rigor of qualitative inquiry must be demonstrated to be considered credible (Polit & Beck, 2017). Ensuring rigor in qualitative analysis can be challenging because it is an interpretative approach to analyzing data. However, its value is substantial when adequately conducted. Faculty mentors (researchers) and the DNP author-maintained self-awareness of personal bias, attitudes, and perceptions regarding collaboration,

through self-interrogation and reflection, to enhance credibility of the findings (Vaismoradi et al., 2016). There were four individuals involved in the analysis and coding decision-making process, which reduced the risk of biases by using investigator triangulation and enhanced the quality and credibility of the findings (Patton, 1999).

Ethical Considerations

The project was approved by the Institutional Review Board (IRB) at California State University, Long Beach. Informed consent was obtained before respondent participation.

RESULTS

The completion of the coding process revealed key concepts and ideas that helped to identify critical elements of collaboration from the providers' perspectives. The perspectives of participants provided insight into collaboration, behaviors that facilitated collaboration, what made collaboration effective, and the disciplines involved. The analysis of narrative responses revealed three themes: collaboration, communication, and IDT. Collaboration was the central theme. Each theme had subthemes that contributed to the understanding of that theme.

Theme 1: Collaboration

Participants' exemplars frequently described the meaning of collaboration and its impact on patient care. Collaboration was a shared interaction among team members that "requires trust, respect, and frequent communication." Participants noted each discipline shared information to optimize patient care. They related how partnerships with others in care activities promoted cohesiveness, created a positive work environment, and allowed for better patient experiences. When collaborating, all team members were working closely together, being supportive of one another, and had a clear understanding of roles and expectations of team members.

Collaboration had three subthemes: process, outcomes, and collaborators. The process of collaboration was the ongoing interactions between healthcare providers to meet patient needs. It consisted of working together, conveying ideas to each other, and working with the entire team both within and outside the institution. For example, a participant spoke to the process of working with other disciplines to meet patient needs.

I am an NP with our Palliative Care team, along with the social worker and care manager we are working with a local hospice agency to continue her current interventions while she is still functionally doing well and remove interventions as appropriate including IV nutrition. We talk several times a day and are talking and working with the patient and family to piece together this difficult discharge situation to meet her goals.

Central to a productive collaboration process was a peer/colleague relationship between providers; however, participants frequently noted that this did not always occur. For example, one respondent wrote about the challenges of working with physicians who view themselves as the primary decision maker and other clinicians as a subservient to their role.

There seems to be a tension related to the roles and expectations, especially between the physician MD and nurse practitioner since both practice independently, write scripts, etc. The physician sees the NP as someone to support his role rather than a peer/colleague.

An essential part of the collaboration process was ensuring consistency and mutual agreements existed among team members regarding patient care goals. When healthcare providers were transparent with patients, families, and other clinicians about goals of care and committed to assuring such goals were met, the team approach was more effective. A respondent discussed how clarification of goals allowed for patient and family wishes to be honored during care plan implementation.

All the time! I met this morning with a family where goals of care were not clear, with the healthcare team on one page, and various family members on various

other pages. A conference was held, clear and consistent medical information was related, questions addressed, and goals of care well delineated. This allowed for agreement on goals, which informed a cohesive plan of care. The patient then received appropriate care, in alignment with patient and family wishes.

The outcomes of collaboration were the result of the work performed cohesively in clinical settings. Several participants associated collaboration with desired outcomes such as positive patient experience, improved quality of care, and making a difference in patient care. For example, a participant reported how collaboration helped clinicians address patient needs beyond symptom management.

We recently cared for a homeless patient and through collaboration were able to get her symptoms under control, assess her financial situation, secure a safe home for her, transfer her to a primary care team and get her moved into her new home. She may have < 6 months to live, but she will be in a safe place she can call her own . . . huge quality bonus!

The outcomes of collaboration improved patient care and involved ongoing interactions among healthcare providers.

Collaborators were healthcare providers from different disciplines who came together to formulate comprehensive care plans that maximized treatment options and optimized patient outcomes. For example, a participant spoke of how each discipline contributed to increased patient satisfaction and achievement of care delivery goals.

I work on an IDT in an outpatient cancer clinic at a large VAMC. We had a patient who was newly diagnosed with Stage IIIa Hodgkin's lymphoma and had a distress score of 9-10 at many of his early appts (appointments). He had a history

of substance abuse, family problems, and financial issues as well as the new diagnosis. The social worker, psychologist, advanced practice nurse and medical oncologist worked collaboratively to help him cope with the diagnosis and start treatment. We were very worried that he would not show up for appts, would not complete treatment and was in danger of resuming old coping strategies (drugs). The psychiatrist met with him at every visit and his distress score slowly decreased to a sustainable 2-3. The social worker helped with his financial and family concerns and the APRN worked to address his chronic back pain and neuropathy with methadone. He told us that he never would have done the treatment if it wasn't for the team helping him at every visit and for the first time in a long time, his chronic pain was much improved. He completed treatment and is currently stable.

Although healthcare providers were the main participants in the collaboration process, the patient and family engagement were also integral for effective collaboration. For care to be patient and family centered, the patient and family had to be actively engaged in the patient's care as well as be included in decisions regarding the patient's health needs and the corresponding needs of the family to promote therapeutic outcomes. For example, a participant discussed how allowing family members to be active participants in meeting patient care goals, enhanced the care experience and care quality.

Referral for elderly female with dementia, who at first evaluation by hospice nurse did not appear to meet criteria. However, follow up phone to spouse revealed patient had "rare" upbeat day and was communicative during the assessment. It took patient 2 days to recover from the effort she put forth for the

nurse. Also, spouse was not forthcoming with patient's true status since she was having a "good" day- he did not want to paint a realistic picture. Follow up phone call to referring physician, evaluation by social worker, evaluation by hospice APRN, and discussion with medical director and hospice RN who performed initial assessment revealed that patient did meet eligibility criteria. She was admitted to hospice services and died within 8 weeks. The hospice IDT team helped to manage her agitation, her declining nutritional status, her declining functional status. Support was provided to her spouse regarding education on death and dying, food and water from a hospice perspective. Her symptoms were managed and she died comfortably. Her spouse had support during his bereavement. Without the persistence and collaboration of the IDT members, this patient may not have had the positive hospice experience that made a difference in her quality of life at the end of life.

Overall, collaboration could not be effective without the consistent engagement of healthcare providers, patients, and families from beginning to end.

Theme 2: Communication

The participants frequently described communication as being "vital," "important," "key," and the "greatest tool." They discussed how communication was a two-way process that required the full participation of those involved. Communication involved sharing information and knowledge, describing information in detail, and listening to facilitate interactions among team members. There were three subthemes identified by participants that outlined the critical aspects of communication and its contribution to effective patient care: process, time, and outcomes.

Respondents frequently wrote that communication and collaboration by the IDT was “necessary,” “essential,” “crucial,” and “key.” The author noted recurring comments from the respondents about the process of communication. They defined the process as consisting of activities that facilitated sending, receiving, and using information in order to meet goals. In addition, information sharing should be effortless and accessible and comprised of actions that require health providers to support and guide one another. For example, a participant spoke of the processes that promoted effective communication.

partnering up and discussing an effective way of delivering healthcare/therapies/interventions, etc. Building trust, establishing rapport, and constant, effective/compassionate communication is ongoing and a must to see positive results.

Information and knowledge sharing among providers promoted understanding of palliative care team principles, provided evidenced-based education to team members, and encouraged active involvement of all members in patient care management. Those activities supported the productive exchange of information and enhanced the communication efforts among healthcare providers. For example, a participant reported on the benefit of conveying detailed information to the team, in order to optimize patient outcomes.

Upon discussion a patient and family, the social worker described the patient’s family situation in detail revealing recent multiple losses. And the now patient’s sister having a staging procedure done today (after learning she had breast cancer). As a team we made the decision to hold off on our goals of treatment discussion until the family can regroup.

Various methods of communication facilitated information sharing in the healthcare setting and were essential components of sending and receiving information between providers. Modes of communicating included face-to-face, email, secure message, phone, text, and care conferences. A participant reported how employing these methods of communicating ensured accurate information was relayed to and understood by all team members.

Our team is excellent. We follow a script when presenting patients in IDT meeting to make sure all areas are covered. We communicate by phone, in person, and by secure messages. We are very patient centered.

Although these methods of communication assisted healthcare providers with delivering relevant health information about patients to colleagues, at times those methods were ineffective due to the communication style, mood, or resistance of the team members. For example, a participant spoke of how the inconsistencies in communication or lack of communication can cause team members to feel excluded.

The collaboration on my team varies depending on the attending physician (we have 3 who rotate) and their style, preference for communication, and mood. Sometimes, with some attendings, everyone feels included and the patient interactions go smoothly. Other times, the day or week feels very fragmented with little communication (be it face to face, verbal via phone, or txt) between not only the clinicians, but the rest of the team as well.

Communication style, mood, or resistance of team members were important aspects of communication, but the types of communication were also an integral part of information sharing among healthcare providers. The forms of communication were

described as close, open, honest, accurate, clear, transparent, constant, and high-level communication. The types of communication influenced how much information was delivered, received, or understood by team members. For example, a participant reported how the communication type determined productivity of team interactions.

Chaplain, Palliative Care RN, physician, SW case manager meeting with family to review goals of care, realistic [*sic*] expectations, exploring hope to establish plan of care. Provided opportunity for clarity for family and staff. Fostered sense of oneness and enhanced the supportive environment for family in making difficult decisions. Opened lines of honest and transparent communication. Family felt safe and supported in making decisions and honoring patient's wishes even though the decisions were in conflict with the family members personal wishes. Communication is the key in ALL end of life situations.

The majority of the participants identified effective communication not only as clearly communicating ideas and openly sharing information, but also as members involved in actively listening to one another. Furthermore, effective communication included grasping the full meaning of what was being said as well as assigned tasks that had to be completed to accomplish care delivery goals. For example, a participant spoke to the impact of communication when team members encouraged patient and family to verbalize preferences or interests during care goal discussions that supported a patient-centered approach to care.

We had a patient with Merkel cell Carcinoma who refused to allow HHA visits and was reluctant to connect with his RN case manager. The chaplain found out about the patient's collection of firefighting equipment and informed the rest of

the staff of the patient's sense of value based in his background as a fireman.

When each staff member made their next visits, they were able to use the collection to engage the patient in opening up and allowing adequate care as his illness progressed.

Several participants also discussed the impact of poor communication or a lack of communication; one participant wrote, "If there is no communication between caregivers, the patient care is affected," and another participant wrote, "Nurses are relied upon to present most of the information. Social services and chaplains tend to not share even if information would be useful to other disciplines." The participants associated poor patient outcomes with withholding or omitting vital information that affected care management or care coordination. Furthermore, participants stressed the importance of team members being consistent, transparent, and specific when communicating to ensure what is heard is congruent with what is conveyed to accomplish goals.

The subtheme of time/frequency involved the time needed or required to ensure the exchange of information occurred and was effective. Participants indicated that providers should be available and present during meetings and care conferences or via phone or email to ensure that all members are having the "same conversations and are on the same page." Frequent communication or "staying in close contact with IDT members" and daily reports on all patients" helped those who could not attend team meetings to stay current with the plan of care and ensured "that there is a good flow of information." In healthcare settings, the component of time not only affected opportunities for providers to talk to one another, but also made optimal delivery of care

challenging. For example, a participant noted how care could be compromised by time constraints that hinder effective communication.

pressure to complete patient care in less time interferes with team communication.

Many times POC (plan of care) is developed without the input of those who spend the most time at the bedside resulting in poorly timed discharges leading to readmits and deaths in other facilities.

The frequency of communication was also influential in healthcare providers' interactions and affected how care goals were accomplished. Many participants discussed how communication should be ongoing, daily, hourly, and on a regular basis.

ALWAYS! IT IS IMPERATIVE IN ASSURING CONTINUITY OF CARE AND EFFECTIVE HOLISTIC CARE. OUR TEAM COMMUNICATES HOURLY, IF NOT MORE FREQUENTLY, IN REGARDS TO CHANGING PATIENT NEEDS, DECLINES, URGENT SITUATIONS [participant capitalized all letters].

The identified outcomes of effective communication were making collaboration easier, guiding the approach to care, and ensuring everyone was in agreement with formulated care goals, which resulted in better consistency and management of care. When healthcare providers were able to “talk multiple times daily” and “meet formally or informally,” communication was effective and clear, thus increasing productivity among team members.

Theme 3: IDT

Respondents frequently reported IDTs as being “essential,” “effective,” “crucial,” and “making a difference.” IDTs were a mix of disciplines working together to meet the

needs of patients cohesively. Teams were formal, such as palliative care teams, or informal, such as collaborators for a specific patient issue, and ranged in size from two to many members. For example, a participant reported how the IDTs were important, as they could accomplish more as a team versus a single entity, and teamwork allowed goals to be achieved efficiently.

Interdisciplinary teams are a very effective way of delivering care to patients and families. It is such relief to families not to hear people saying “That’s not my job or that’s not my responsibility” but instead take care of the patient/family’s problem quickly and efficiently.

Participants discussed their experiences related to working in a team and how teamwork influenced patient care. There were three subthemes identified: actions, time, and outcomes.

The actions of team members were behaviors that promoted collaboration and mutual goal setting. The behaviors of team members that participants discussed consisted of getting together, having case conferences to discuss patient information, meeting with families, and coordinating activities that facilitated treatment approaches. When healthcare providers demonstrated such behaviors, interactions were productive and cohesive. A participant reported how meeting and getting together with other disciplines to discuss goals of care and address family/patient or provider differences were effective actions that promoted an IDT approach.

Each discipline outlines their goals for resident care. When a resident fails to reach their nutritional goals and interventions prove to be unsuccessful, the discussion of palliative care becomes very important. Often, it is the nutritional

program that identifies this initial failure to thrive. Without the IDT input into the overall plan, the opportunity to miss this very important component of care transition is great. It is the difference between providing comfort, support and love or aggressively encouraging repair and advancement. Without this collaboration, we fail to hear the resident's verbal and non-verbal communication.

The contributions of each discipline were a significant part of the team approach to patient care. One participant wrote, "I believe strong interdisciplinary teams value all members of the team and the skills each bring to the table and do not take for granted that those skills are outside their practice." Healthcare providers respecting "other's knowledge and practice" were key elements of IDTs that "enhances the team experience," "guide the development of patient care goals," and "leads to better quality care for the patient and family." In addition, participants noted that when team members did not acknowledge other's expertise or worked well together, the patient and family lacked confidence in the decision-making ability of healthcare providers. An example was a quadriplegic patient who had been hospitalized for 1 year and experienced several complications. Once the palliative care team became involved, the participant discovered that the "wife and patient feel as if no one is making decisions . . . 'limbo-land.'" This supports how important it is for all team members to have mutually shared beliefs and understanding about patient care goals when formulating as well as implementing treatment decisions. Overall, participants believed that IDTs were vital to patient care and all members involved should actively come together, share information, acknowledge the expertise of others, and participate in cohesive decision making to optimize care.

Participants reported variations in expectations regarding meeting frequency. While most reported that providers should “meet daily as a team,” others indicated teams needed to meet weekly to “review patient and family needs” and “provide support to clinicians” to ensure consistency of care goals. For example, a participant spoke about how a dedicated meeting time was considered significant because not all members could attend team meetings due to staffing, workload, or lack of interest, thus missing the opportunity to participate in team discussions.

I fully embrace the IDT model, however I am the only one in the palliative care department - and have another department training parish nurses that I am also the only person. In a hospital I have run into problems with IDT meetings (other departments can't get free during that time; limited interest in other departments to attend; etc.) I believe that PC IDT meetings are valuable to all concerned. Am considering how to change the hospice IDT weekly meeting model into one that is more conducive to hospital stays of a couple of days.

The ability to meet was often an issue. As one participant said, “Our team is struggling with the volume of work and an ability to meet and to discuss patient care plans.” When healthcare providers were unable to meet or attend care conferences, it hampered the discussion of care goals and formulation of cohesive approaches to care delivery. Being allotted time to attend case conferences, family meetings, and team-based meetings improved the care being delivered, and most participants said all members of the team supported it. Leadership can influence providers being able to attend team meetings. The participants reported that a team-based approach to care should be promoted and supported by the healthcare leadership team. Healthcare leaders

allotting time for team meetings, enforcing teamwork as the culture, and assigning team building activities in clinical settings not only promoted optimal patient outcomes, but also encouraged a productive team environment. For example, regardless of the frequency of meetings, respondents perceived that consistently meeting with team members and having support from the leadership team was essential to achieving goals of care as well as added value to the team experience.

Having leaders who inspire folks to want to do their best, for themselves and for their patients; leaders who guide and educate staff and who use every opportunity as a teachable moment help inspire their teams to do amazing work.

The outcomes of using and implementing an interdisciplinary approach to patient care were beneficial. The power in sharing knowledge and using the expertise of others to improve patient outcomes was incomparable. Many participants agreed that working together as a team or in an IDT enhanced quality of care; one participant stated, “When we get a big thank you from patients and families, we know our teamwork contribute to their satisfaction,” and another participant stated, “Nearly every time—different perspectives from SW, chaplains, nurses and physicians are invaluable.” Some respondents reported that equality promoted effective teamwork.

It is wonderful to work with an organization that truly uses an interdisciplinary approach. Everyone’s opinion and input are treated equally. Everyone respects everyone else and is highly dedicated. The quality of care is very high.

There was consensus that when healthcare teams were unable to work together and used a silo approach to care, patient outcomes were negatively affected. Examples of several key points raised related to a silo approach to care included the following issues.

Healthcare providers should not withhold information from other members because this action could result in fragmented delivery of care. A silo approach to patient care did not support or encourage the involvement of other disciplines to manage complex health needs of patients, which then became a barrier to the IDT approach in clinical settings. Adverse outcomes associated with the silo approach mentality included disciplines isolating or separating themselves, overlooking nonmedical disciplines, tension about roles and expectations, and teams not working well together. For example, a participant reported how ineffective partnerships can hinder care goal achievements.

In palliative care it is so important to have a well working interdisciplinary team. For a few years, our team was not working well together. It was like two separate entities, social workers and APRNS now it is going in the right direction. The two disciplines have to collaborate and share information or it's only the patient who suffers.

To ensure that an interdisciplinary approach is employed, team members should view team members as a peer or counterpart versus separate entities. However, this was not always the perception. One participant stated that the "IDT is not necessary in many or even most encounters. 'The Conversation' can be managed by the physician alone." However, most respondents noted that there should be greater alignment and clinical integration of all disciplines to transform the organizational culture of hierarchical roles that may exist in many clinical settings.

Conclusion

In conclusion, participants identified experiences with collaboration, communication, and IDTs that provided insight into team-based care. Collaboration was

the central theme. However, communication and IDTs were essential for collaboration to be successful. Critical elements of teamwork identified by the participants were used to generate practice recommendations to enhance collaborative practice and improve care for veterans.

DISCUSSION

This section discusses the interpretation and significance of the qualitative results in light of what the literature and the analysis revealed. The qualitative results affirmed the significance of collaboration in healthcare settings. The three themes that emerged from the data demonstrated how providers interpret opportunities and challenges related to a team-based care approach. Participant narratives identified the key aspects of collaboration. The participants frequently identified collaboration as interactive, ongoing, and occurring frequently. Respondents noted that collaboration involved people working together consistently to meet patient care goals. Overall, participants believed that collaboration guided care delivery and should be encouraged.

The respondents' views about collaboration, communication, and IDT were mostly positive and supported the findings discussed in the literature review. The literature review identified that provider perceptions of collaboration are influenced by three elements that affect the formation and sustainment of teams: (a) misconceptions of professional roles, (b) poor communication, and (c) lack of interprofessional education. Provider perceptions of collaboration (whether occurring or not occurring) is significant, because it determines team effectiveness. Several respondents expressed how collaboration fostered trust, improved symptom control, and enhanced achievement of care goals. However, when collaboration did not occur, respondents expressed that care plans could not be formulated, and patient care suffered. How providers view one another's contribution or value one another's contribution establishes the foundation for team development and can be very impactful in clinical settings.

Provider perceptions about collaborative practice in clinical settings are important because the individuals facilitate this interactive process. Without full cooperation and participation of all members, cohesiveness is hindered. The qualitative findings support the notion that collaborators who actively engaged in ongoing interactions maximize patient outcomes by sharing knowledge and using different expert approaches to address patient health needs. All team members should participate in discussions about patient care, convey information that is useful, and engage in the decision-making process. However, when misconceptions about professional roles exist, collaborative practice approaches are diminished. According to the literature review, there is an unspoken hierarchical order in clinical settings, placing the physician as the dominant decision maker (Garber et al., 2009; Lancaster et al., 2015; Weinberg et al., 2011). Some respondents spoke to the existence of a hierarchy in their experience with physicians, recommending that hierarchies be flattened to promote collaborative interactions. A participant also spoke about physicians not having insight into roles of other disciplines and nonlicensed staff. The participant believed this impeded the collaboration process because nonlicensed personnel and other disciplines are not included in discussions about care goals or part of the decision-making process.

To change misconceptions and gain a better understanding of other team members' roles, providers should be aware of the responsibilities and limitations of other clinicians. Healthcare providers should be open minded to the expertise of others and show interest in using the skill set of others to achieve optimal outcomes. It is crucial that all members of the healthcare team contribute to improving patient outcomes. Inputting ideas, listening to the ideas of others, respecting others, and using the

knowledge of others are key factors that promote therapeutic discussions and foster a sense of oneness among team members as noted by participants. Consulting and discussing all aspects that influence goal attainment in patient care settings should be the priority among team members. Furthermore, soliciting help from others should always be encouraged in all healthcare settings.

In addition to soliciting help from others, being able to verbalize the need for assistance is essential and can affect collaborative interactions. In this project, participants identified communication as a critical component of care quality, which is consistent across multiple studies (Clapper & Kong, 2012; Lisbon et al., 2016). Communication is a significant part of collaboration and is not always easy. Healthcare providers typically use various methods of communication to send and receive vital information on patient care. Providers should be comfortable and confident in their ability to relay information to others in a succinct concise way. Researchers suggest that healthcare providers receive training on how to use all electronic devices to facilitate effective communication. Providers should know how to navigate the EMR. Understanding how to use electronic devices helps providers efficiently send and receive information. In addition to education on technology to facilitate communication, healthcare providers need information on how to communicate appropriately. Healthcare providers should possess excellent listening skills, not use language that feels critical to team members, provide good eye contact, be mindful of body language, and allot time for effective exchange of information to occur. When those components are not used, it can influence how the message is received, which hinders goal accomplishment.

The literature discussed how fragmented communication can cause failures in collaboration and medical errors due to the ambiguity of the message being delivered, systematic issues with EMR systems, and lack of accountability for task completion (Arnold & Boggs, 2015; Robinson et al., 2010). In our analysis, participants discussed information transfer as being impeded by the same issues. Participants discussed how the EMR is supposed to be helpful or makes things more manageable but complicated things instead. Others believed that during transfers of care, providers tend to shift responsibility of care without proper hand-off or sufficient information to ensure continuity of care persists.

Continuity of care and consistency in care delivery are facilitated by communication that should be concise, clear, and transparent. In addition to clarity and transparency, all methods of communication (verbal, phone, email, text message, instant message, progress notes, meetings) should be used to exchange information that is essential to optimizing outcomes. For this process to be effective, those involved should not withhold or omit information that influences patient care. When team members share a consensus on patient care goals and are willing to collaborate effectively, the experience is invaluable for the team members, patients, and families.

To facilitate communication among healthcare providers, team members should be present in meetings or case conferences to share their expertise about care or treatment options, no matter if differing opinions exist. It is not enough to just sit next to one another, speak on the phone, or send an email; ongoing active engagement and discussion must occur for true collaboration to work. Because of the varied methods of communication available in healthcare settings, communication should be standardized

for all providers, even those in residency or contracted employees, to promote uniformity as well as decrease communication errors. In addition, the methods of communication should be accessible to all providers and properly working to facilitate effective communication. It is important for team members to continually communicate with each other, support each other, share responsibilities, and look out for each other's needs. Encouraging participation and involvement of all disciplines provides support, facilitates communication, and makes a difference in patient care.

Collaboration is more than just the team. The clinicians from different disciplines and specialties ensure diversity exists among the groups who are collaborating. Collaboration is the active engagement of those diverse disciplines working together to achieve goals. To promote collaboration in clinical settings, it has to be implemented and encouraged by healthcare leaders. The literature review did not speak to the influence or role of leadership in collaborative practice. However, in the TeamSTEPPS model, healthcare leaders in clinical practice settings are accountable for fostering a collaborative culture and promoting teamwork, which is why leadership is another important component of collaboration. The leadership team impacts how and when collaboration is occurring in healthcare settings, which is crucial to team sustainment. For collaboration to exist and thrive in healthcare environments, it must be instituted from the top down. In our analysis, collaborative interactions were much more effective and efficient when leadership was supportive and assisted in team processes. A respondent spoke of the medical director or administrators being involved in working to problem solve a patient care issue so that outcomes are optimized, and team processes are enhanced.

The leadership of an organization significantly influences the ability for individuals to collaborate efficiently. Healthcare leaders establish organizational culture and should ensure that all barriers that interfere with collaborative practice are removed. The qualitative findings suggest that healthcare leaders should ensure clinicians have the necessary resources to function as a collective unit versus a separate entity to facilitate team effectiveness. Healthcare leaders allotting protected time to conduct and attend meetings or discussions about patient and unit needs can increase team productivity. Leadership should encourage providers to perform tasks together (i.e., attend team building courses), participate in team building activities, and evaluate team productivity to enhance collaboration. The delineation between working among colleagues versus working with colleagues should be described and explained in the healthcare environment. Furthermore, healthcare leaders should discourage hierarchal behaviors and approaches to care delivery and should encourage each discipline to function as equal participants in healthcare settings. Once the leadership team remove barriers to collaboration, and team-based behaviors are praised, providers will become more comfortable with including others versus separating themselves when addressing patient care issues.

The analysis reflects similar studies that identified a lack of formal interprofessional education as contributing to providers isolating themselves from team members (Barnsteiner et al., 2007; Rosenstein, 2002; Wanzer et al., 2009). Several authors suggest that healthcare providers are socialized and trained to practice as separate entities in clinical settings (Barnsteiner et al., 2007). Silo approaches to care may be the most widely used approach in healthcare settings where the physician is the primary

decision maker and everyone else is carrying out the decisions made by physicians. However, all healthcare providers involved in patient care can contribute to the decision-making process to improve outcomes. Every healthcare provider has a different experience with patients and serves in various roles that generate ideas or knowledge to benefit patient care. Providers should embrace inclusiveness as a method for improving patient outcomes. No single provider can meet the needs of patients, so a team-based approach is integral to care quality. Many times, providers have the mantra of “that’s not my job” as reported by one of the participants and is a barrier to collaboration/team-based care approach.

To decrease the use of a silo approach and increase a team-based approach, the author suggests healthcare providers gain knowledge about the scope of practice of other disciplines. Providers also need to understand the limitations and responsibilities of other disciplines to understand how their role contributes to meeting care goals. Providers’ willingness to seek out assistance from other disciplines, attend team meetings, openly discuss one another’s expertise as it pertains to maximizing treatment options, and requesting the opinions of others can decrease the silo approach to care delivery. Furthermore, providers willing to reach out to other disciplines before independently making decisions can promote collaborative practice. Clinicians’ being able to share knowledge on patient care between providers ensures that interactions are productive and team members fully comprehend the goals of care.

Collaboration should be everyone’s right and everyone’s responsibility, including healthcare leaders. The DNP author suggests that for healthcare to move forward and truly be patient centered, all providers should be able to contribute their knowledge and

experiences to improve patient care. The act of collaboration is not new but will always be challenging in healthcare settings if a culture of collaboration is not the standard. The takeaway message from participant exemplars is that collaboration is about bringing one's best self and helping others bring their best self to focus on a common goal while making a positive impact on patient care.

In summary, the literature and qualitative findings support collaboration, communication, and an IDT approach as improving patient outcomes. Qualitative results provided clear meanings of collaboration, communication, and IDTs that include key factors that influenced effectiveness of each concept. The findings also offered insight into the individuals involved in the collaborative process, factors that impaired or enhanced shared interactions, and the role communication played in ensuring there is a universal understanding among healthcare providers, thus explaining the limited existence of a team-based care approach in clinical settings.

Changing provider perspectives and the overall culture on collaborative practice in clinical settings is challenging. For this change to be effective, it requires the constant effort of leadership and healthcare providers acknowledging the benefit of a team-based approach. In addition, leaders and providers must work diligently to sustain a collaborative model of care. The TeamSTEPPS teamwork model is a tool used in clinical settings to transform practice by decreasing formation of silos and fostering a team-based approach to care delivery. The four competencies (communication, leadership, situational monitoring, and mutual support) in this model support the themes identified in the qualitative findings. This conceptual model describes the importance of healthcare providers working in teams, sharing knowledge, communicating efficiently, receiving

support from leadership, and providing feedback to one another to promote optimal functioning of team processes, which were critical factors reinforced by participant responses. Each competency builds upon one another and guides healthcare systems on how to formulate and sustain high functioning clinical teams. For this reason, the author developed practice recommendations based upon the qualitative findings and the TeamSTEPPS conceptual teamwork model, which will guide clinicians on how to collaborate and communicate effectively.

PRACTICE RECOMMENDATIONS

The DNP author based the following practice recommendations on finding from the qualitative analysis of the open text responses from care providers (Goebel et al., 2016) as well as evidence reported in the review of literature related to care quality and TeamSTEPPS. The author synthesized these sources to develop recommendations consistent with the mission and goals of the VHA. The practice recommendations aim to enhance collaboration among healthcare providers within the VHA to improve outcomes for veterans.

The concept of teamwork in hospitals has become an integral component of various healthcare initiatives of care delivery re-designed to improve patient outcomes (Robert Wood Johnson Foundation, 2010). However, communication failures, organization compliancy, localization of physicians on specified units, time, and workplace culture influence initiation and sustainment of high-functioning healthcare teams. Although communication is a significant component of influencing healthcare outcomes, the central theme identified in the qualitative findings was collaboration. However, communication and IDTs were other themes that contributed to the success of collaborative processes and were necessary for an effective team-based approach to care delivery, also supported by the TeamSTEPPS conceptual model. Based on the qualitative findings, the DNP author developed the following practice recommendations to improve collaborative care for veterans across healthcare settings. They aligned with the four competencies of the TeamSTEPPS model.

TeamSTEPPS

TeamSTEPPS is an evidence-based training model that promotes a set of tools to enhance teamwork and collaboration. The four competencies (mutual support, communication, leadership, and situational monitoring) provided a conceptual foundation for this project and were employed to formulate practice recommendations for healthcare providers caring for the veteran population.

Practice Recommendations: Mutual Support

Mutual support requires that healthcare providers are willing and prepared to assist one another, provide feedback to one another, and share workload tasks to decrease burnout or stress. The VHA can employ the following tasks to enhance mutual support among healthcare providers and foster a collaborative environment while improving care for veterans:

1. Healthcare providers should meet and get together to discuss care coordination and goals of care.
 - a. Attend case conferences, team meetings, and family meetings.
 - b. Use document manager computerized software that provides automatic reminders of team meetings to prevent nonattendance.
 - c. Actively engage in discussions with other providers.
 - d. Take initiative to solicit providers from other disciplines when formulating plans of care to optimize outcomes.
2. Healthcare providers should not separate themselves or act as separate entities when formulating or implementing decisions about patient care.
 - a. Clearly define roles and responsibilities in clinical settings that team members can understand.
 - b. Use objective versus subjective language during patient care discussions in and outside of healthcare settings.
 - c. Use terms such as “we” or “us” when discussing implementation of care plans.

- d. Perform rounds with other disciplines to demonstrate to patients and families that the care approach is a team effort.
 - e. Clarify all duties of each team member before and after care coordination to promote consistency of task completion and accomplishment of care goals.
3. Healthcare providers should respect and appreciate the expertise and contributions of all members as well as solicit the expertise of others when coordinating care in order to facilitate workload sharing and provider burnout.
 - a. Consult with specialty providers about complicated and/or patient care dilemmas.
 - b. Consult with all members of the team including nonlicensed staff to enhance the team approach.
 - c. Allow all providers involved in the patient's care to share ideas and treatment approaches that addresses other aspects of the patient's health that influence outcomes.
 4. Healthcare providers should perform quarterly assessments or evaluations of peers to improve team performance.

The goal of mutual support is to enhance social support among team members by engaging in behaviors that result in sharing responsibilities, clarifying roles, respecting the roles of others, receiving and using peer feedback (negative or positive), and decreasing issues that create conflict among healthcare providers. The VHA can encourage their employees to demonstrate such behaviors by using assessment tools and team building activities that identify deficits among team members and implementing activities that strengthen those deficiencies.

Practice Recommendations: Communication

Communication promotes teamwork by causing team members to convey and utilize relevant information and use relevant information to achieve mutual goals.

Communication should be clear, concise, and understood by all team members. The

VHA can employ the following tasks to improve communication among healthcare professionals while improving care for veterans:

1. Communication should be interactive and ongoing.
 - a. Appoint a communication liaison or champion in patient care units who monitors and encourages positive behaviors to promote effective exchange of information.
 - b. Create a checklist of team goals when engaging in patient care to ensure all team members understand the goals of care.
 - c. Use a teach back or recall back strategy when discussing patient care tasks to ensure the appropriate plan of care is implemented.
2. All methods of communication should ensure accurate and effective exchange of information.
 - a. Modes of communication should be properly working and accessible to all providers (i.e., phones, extensions, emails, pagers, voicemail, etc.).
 - b. Standardize and make mandatory the use of hand-off tools during patient care (i.e., SBAR, IPASS, call-out).
 - c. Create standardized templates in the EMR system for transitions of care.
 - d. Collaborate with other healthcare institutions to develop EMR software that foster information sharing to optimize patient care.
 - e. Have a policy in place related to actions when team members do not communicate respectfully, well, or in a timely manner.

The goal of communication is to shape the culture of the organization and dictate how team members send, transfer, and receive information. The channels used to share information should be effective and nonfragmented.

Practice Recommendations: Leadership

Leadership involves appointed leaders ensuring that team members are demonstrating behaviors that foster a team environment. Healthcare leaders are responsible for continuously monitoring team members' performance and productivity in

the patient care environment as well as educating them on improving teamwork.

Healthcare leaders at the VHA should employ and adhere to the following tasks to improve collaboration and communication among healthcare professionals while improving care for veterans:

1. Perform culture assessments on units that identify deficits in communication and collaboration among healthcare providers (including residents and medical students).
2. Develop and implement an interprofessional education curriculum and make it mandatory for employees to complete.
3. Facilitate and prioritize team meetings to promote effective communication.
4. Implement tour of duty hours that allot time for team building activities (i.e., project planning, group tasks).
5. Provide rewards and incentives for team productivity.
6. Develop policies and procedures that foster teamwork and require employees to adhere to them.
7. Establish partnerships with community organizations that increase access to services for veterans (i.e., transportation, housing) and encourage healthcare providers to reach out to community organizations to bridge the gap for veterans.
8. Establish partnerships with education institutions to increase recruitment of healthcare providers.
9. Revise hiring plan of nurse practitioners and physicians by increasing entry-level positions for those disciplines.

Practice Recommendations: Situational Monitoring

Situational monitoring involves team members developing a model that fosters a team-based approach and prompt identification of issues that hinder team behaviors. The VHA can employ the following tasks to improve collaboration and communication among healthcare professionals while improving care for veterans:

1. Appoint a conflict resolution champion on units.

2. Develop survey tools that allow employees to assess one another's strengths and weaknesses.
3. Appoint team leaders or team champions on patient care units and allow rotation of team leaders.
4. Implement briefs, huddles, debriefs, and rounding in all departments/patient care units to promote sharing of information and feedback.
5. Implement team models of care that place all healthcare team members on the same level. Although physicians are responsible for initiating the treatment and developing the care plan, nurses and other disciplines are responsible for implementing the care plan, ensuring the plan is effective, and speaking up when the plan is not working, which means everyone's role matters and should be valued.

Evaluation Plan for Recommendations

The author's evaluation plan for the development of practice recommendations will involve the following:

- Identify how the VHA defines collaboration.
- Explore survey data about collaboration at the VHA.
- Develop recommendations considering findings from the data analysis to meet the health needs of veterans.
- Present recommendations to Director of Nursing at the VHA for review, solicit feedback, and revise recommendations implementing feedback provided.
- Present recommendations to clinical practice area, solicit feedback, and revise recommendations based upon feedback provided.
- Disseminate recommendations across all VHA settings (in California) to promote a team-based care approach to veterans' care.

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